

YO'L HARAKATI QOIDALARIDA TRANSPORT TUSHUNCHASI

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Farg'ona viloyati Oltiariq tumani

2 son kasb hunar maktabi yo'l harakati qoidalari fani o'qituvchisi

Annotasiya: Maqolada transport tushunchasi, terminning ma'nosi, transport tizimini shakllanishi, suv, xavo va quruqlikdagi transport vositalarining yo'l xarakatidagi ahamiyatiga qisqacha to'xtalinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Transport, joy, aloqa, tizim, vosita.

Аннотация: В статье кратко рассмотрены понятие транспорта, значение термина, формирование транспортной системы, значение водного, воздушного и наземного транспорта в дорожном движении.

Ключевые слова: Транспорт, место, связь, система, инструмент.

Abstract: The article briefly discusses the concept of transport, the meaning of the term, the formation of the transport system, the importance of water, air and land vehicles in road traffic.

Keywords: Transport, place, communication, system, vehicle.

Transportning rivojlanishi inson jamiyatining taraqqiyoti bilan uzviy bog'liq. Transport (lotin tilidan trans – «orqali» va portare «tashimoq»)–bu xom-ashyo ishlab chiqarishning muhim vositasi, yuk va yo'lovchilarni tashishni amalga oshiradigan; hamma aloqa yo'llarining to'plami, transport vositalari, aloqa yo'llaridagi texnik qurilma va inshootlar, bir joydan ikkinchi joyga turli maqsadlarda yuk va yo'lovchilarni tashish jarayonini ta'minlaydi. Zamonaviy transport (ijtimoiy – iqtisodiy nuqtai nazardan) butun transport tizimini tashkil qiladi.

XX asrda to'liq shakllangan butun dunyo transport tizimi o'z ichiga aloqa yo'llarini (temir va avtomobil magistrali, suv va havo yo'llari, vokzallar va aeroportlar, portlar va stansiyalar), yer usti, havo, suv yo'llarining hamma turlarini qamrab olgan transport vositalari, transport boshqaruvi va korxonalarini olgan. Bu tizim butun aloqa yo'llari bo'ylab yuk va yo'lovchi aylanmasining sifatli va miqdorli ko'rsatkichlariga ega.

Transport - bu bir necha insonlarning individual talablaridan yoki ularning funksiyalaridan shakllangan, yuk va yo'lovchilarni tashish bo'yicha ijtimoiy talabni qondirishga mo'ljallangan inson jamiyatining infrastrukturasidir. Insonlar har doim fazoda tez harakat qilishni orzu qilishgan va osmondagi qushlarga hovas ko'zi bilan qarashgan. Kelajakda aynan sivilizasiya rivojlanishini belgilovchi omil fazoda tez harakat qilish omili bo'ladi. Texnika va transport zamonaviy texnologiyalar rivojlanishida tezlik bilan kurashish rivojlanishining asosiy yo'nalishini belgilaydi. Insonlar hayotidagi moddiy va ma'naviy darajani ko'tarishda keng qamrovli va qiyin muammolarni aynan transport tizimi yechadi. Transport – jamiyatning ishlab chiqarish kuchi vositasidir, bu kuchsiz jamiyatning rivojlanishi va mavjud bo'lishi mumkin emas.

Transport tizimining umumiy strukturasi kapital sarmoyaning ahamiyatli hajmini aloqa yo'llari egallaydi. Harakat tarkibining ishlashsamarasi aloqa yo'llarining holatiga chambarchas bog'liqdir. Ishlatiladigan har bir transport turining nomiga asosan aloqa yo'llari turlicha nomlanadi: avtomobil yo'llari va ko'chalar, temir yo'llari, tramvay yo'llari, metropolitan yo'llari, quvur yo'llari, dengiz yo'llari, daryo yo'llari, havo yo'llari, havo trassalari, relsli, relssiz va boshqalar.

Transport – iqtisodiyotning eng muhim tarmoqlaridan biri hisoblanadi. U jamiyatning moddiy bazasi hisoblanadi, mehnatning taqsimlanishi, xalqaro ishlab chiqarish va savdodagi birlik va mutanosiblik darajasini muvofiqlashtiradi. Transport moddiy ishlab chiqarish tarmog'iga tegishli hisoblanadi, lekin qishloq

xo'jaligidan tashqari biror bir sohada moddiy mahsulot ishlab chiqarishda ishlatilmaydi. U odamlarni va oldindan ishlab chiqarilgan moddiy mahsulotlarni tashishni ta'minlaydi. Turli transportning so'zsiz tashqi farqiga qaramay, ularning qurilishida, saqlanishida va ekspluatasiyasida ko'plab o'xshash jihatlari mavjud. Temiryo'l va avtomobil yo'llaridagi ko'tarmalar va daryodagi yo'naltiruvchi inshootlar konstruksiyalari bir biriga yaqindir. Amaliyotda avtomobil yo'llarini, temir yo'llarni, aerodromlarni yer osti suvlaridan va yer usti suvlaridan himoya qilish bir xil usul orqali yechimini topadi. Daryo va dengiz portlaridagi, avtomobil yo'llaridagi, aerodromlardagi, shahar ko'chalaridagi qoplamalar faqat ayrim detallari orqali bir-biridan farq qiladi. Shuning uchun ishlayotgan muxandis, qaysi transportda ishlashidan qat'iy nazar, boshqa transport turlari haqida ham aniq bilim va ko'nikmalari bo'lishi shart. Mazkur darslikni to'laqonli o'rganish transport tizimi haqida muxandisning dunyoqarashini kengaytiradi va erudisiyasini oshiradi, transport tizimining holatini real baholashni o'rgatadi, uning rivojlanishidagi texnik siyosatni va asosiy ilmiy – tadqiqot ishlarning yo'nalishlarini belgilaydi.

“Transport” termini lotin tilidan “transporto” “ko'chiraman, yetkazaman, tashiyman” degan ma'nolarni anglatadi. Bu so'zda transportning asosiy ma'nosi - odamlarni, narsalarni, hayvonlarni, yuklarni bir joydan ikkinchi joyga tashish, ko'chirish degan ma'noni bildiradi. Biroq, bu termin boshlang'ich ma'nosidan tashqari boshqa ma'nolarni ham berar ekan. Ya'ni, ma'lum bir kontekstda bu termin quyidagi tushunchalarni anglatadi:

1.Yuk va yo'lovchilarni tashish tushunchasini o'z ichiga oladigan xalq xo'jaligi sohasi.

2.Moddiy mahsulotlar va odamlarning tashishini ta'minlaydigan texnik vositalar kompleksi.

3.Fazoda yuk va yo'lovchilarni tashish jarayoni, ko'pincha “transportirovka” so'zi bilan ifodalanadi.

4.Suvda (kema), ko'chada yoki yo'lda (avtomobil) harakatlanuvchi transport birligining oqimi.

5.Aniq belgilangan joyga ma'lum adres bo'yicha yo'naltirilgan yukning aloxida partiyasi.

6. Inson faoliyatining turi yoki mutaxassisligi.

Moddiy ishlab chiqarishning turli sohasi uchun to'g'ri keladigan transportning barcha zarur uchta elementlari:

- mehnat vositalari, ya'ni transport vositalari;
- mehnat predmetlari, tashish obektlari (yuklar va yo'lovchilari);
- insonlarning maqsadli faoliyati, ya'ni mehnat.

Aynan transportda ishlab chiqarish jarayoni – jo'nash punktidan belgilangan punktga yuk va yo'lovchilarning harakatlanishi, transportning tayyor mahsuloti – ularning tugatilgan tashilishi. Bunda shuni e'tiborga olish kerakki, moddiy ishlab chiqarishning boshqa sohalariga nisbatan transport mahsuloti bir vaqtning o'zida ishlab chiqariladi va ishlatiladi, demak, uni ko'proq tayyorlash yoki ishlab chiqarib va zahirada saqlab, kutilmagan uzilish vaqtida yoki joriy ishlab chiqarishning rejalashtirilgan pasayishi vaqtida uni keyin ishga tushirish mumkin bo'lgan moddiy ishlab chiqarish mahsulotidan farqliroq zaxiralash mumkin emas. Bu nuqtai nazardan har qaysi boshqa moddiy ishlab chiqarishdan ko'ra, transport judayam murakkab sohani tashkil qiladi.

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